

Dynamic Research on Urban Morphology books - 7

PANDEMICS AND THE CHANGING BUILT ENVIRONMENT LEARNING FROM HISTORY, PLANNING OUR FUTURE

Proceedings of the First International ONLINE conference, on
Pandemics and Urban Form, PUF2022, April 28th-30th 2022, Istanbul,
Turkey

Edited by

Alessandro Camiz

DRUM Press
Istanbul, 2024

-I-

PANDEMICS AND THE CHANGING BUILT ENVIRONMENT. LEARNING FROM HISTORY, PLANNING OUR FUTURE

Proceedings of the First International ONLINE conference, on Pandemics and Urban Form, PUF2022

April 28th-30th 2022, Istanbul, Turkey

Edited by:

Alessandro Camiz

DRUM Press, Istanbul, 2024

ISBN: 978-1-4452-2385-8

Printed by Lulu.com, Raleigh, NC, USA

Dynamic Research on Urban Morphology books, 7

Book series directed by Alessandro Camiz

<http://labs.ozyegin.edu.tr/drum/books/>

Copyright © 2024 Alessandro Camiz

Cover image:

Thomas Cole, *The Course of Empire. Destruction*, oil on canvas, 1836, New York Historical Society, New York City, NY, US.

All the Papers in this volume were double blind peer-reviewed by the conference's scientific committee

First International ONLINE conference, on Pandemics and Urban Form, PUF2022, April 28th-30th 2022, Istanbul, Turkey
First International online conference, on Pandemics and Urban Form, PUF2022, April 28th-30th 2022, Istanbul, Turkey, Pandemics and the changing built environment. Learning from history, planning our future

Organised by:

INTBAU, Nanjing University, University of Trento, Özyeğin University, and University of Idaho, Kuwait University

With the patrociny of:

International Seminar on Urban Form - ISUF

"Storia della città", Centro internazionale di studi per la storia della città, fonti d'archivio e patrimonio architettonico-ambientale

ISUF-ITALY

Cyprus Network of Urban Morphology CyNUM

pandemicsandurbanform@gmail.com

<https://pandemicsandurbanform.ozyegin.edu.tr/>

<https://cmt3.research.microsoft.com/PUF2022/>

Özyeğin University, Faculty of Architecture and Design, Dynamic Research on Urban Morphology-DRUM laboratory, Diachronic transformations of the built environment

<https://labs.ozyegin.edu.tr/drum>

Table of contents	5
The conference	11
Wowo Ding	
Alessandro Camiz	
Mohammed Alajmi	
Xiao Hu	
Mosè Ricci	
Editor's note	17
<i>Pandemics and Urban form: The Course of Empire</i>	18
Alessandro Camiz	
Keynote speakers	25
Keynote papers	31
<i>Radical change, or just more of the same? Thoughts on COVID and urban change</i>	32
Peter J. Larkham	
Papers	47
<i>Pandemics and climate change. Towards a new territorial cycle and morphological period</i>	48
Alessandro Camiz	
<i>A small investigation on the effects of applying market rules in public spaces and architectures in everyday life and during a pandemic crisis</i>	64
Giorgio Verdiani	
<i>Walls of the present time. Reformulation of the relationship between the individual and the territory</i>	74
Silvia Dalzero	
<i>The Rediscovery of our Dwelling Space during Covid-19</i>	84
Mustapha El Moussaoui	
<i>Holy Spirit Hospices in Mecklenburg – charitable institutions in the urban tissue of the 13th and 14th century</i>	94
Martin Ebert	
Fred Ruchhöf	
Gudrun Ruchhöf	
Philip Hansen	
<i>Extramural Chapels in the medieval towns of Mecklenburg</i>	108
Fred Ruchhöf	
Gudrun Ruchhöf	
Martin Ebert	
Philip Hansen	

<i>Between Emotional Management and Real (Infra). Structural Response: Covid-19 in the Peripheries of Barcelona</i>	120
Sena Aydin Bergfalk	
<i>Post-Pandemic Public Spaces: Strategies for Resilient Parks in the Wake of COVID-19</i>	128
Nirupama Sam	
Neetu Kapoor	
<i>General strategies for post-pandemic public parks</i>	132
<i>The sanatorium typology, its relationship with nature and its influence on Berlin's urban morphology</i>	138
Daniele Roccaro	
<i>Hospital epidemic preparedness: a checklist and case studies</i>	148
Rossella Marmo	
Lorenzo Diana	
Claudia Sicignano	
Francesco Polverino	
Andrej Tibaut	
<i>Morpho-typological relationships between architecture and pandemics: The cases of plague and TBC</i>	158
Raffaele Tarallo	
<i>Evolution of Hospital Typology in 19th and 20th century Algiers, Algeria. Maillot el Kettar hospital and Mustapha Hospitals</i>	170
Khettab Samira	
<i>Historical correlation between pandemics, architecture and urban planning</i>	180
Stefania Farina	
Camilla Mileto	
Fernando Vegas	
<i>Impact of Covid'19 on Space-use in Compact Multi-Family Residential Highrise Apartment Houses: a case of Surat and Ahmedabad</i>	192
Jitendra Menghani	
Rachana Patel	
Chintan Shah	
<i>LOCKdown Dictionary: Daily Life Practices in Pandemic + Post Pandemic Era</i>	204
Nagehan Acimuz Isbakan	
Hulya Turgut	
Buse Usta	
<i>Re-shaping the Contemporary City. Insights from 'KM0 – Displaying Perceptions of Quarantine Landscape'</i>	216
<i>Urban layout (a)temporality in pandemic times. The case of Almirante Reis Avenue, Lisbon</i>	226
Sérgio Proença	

Nawaf Saeed Al Mushayt	
André Lourenço	
<i>CUM-DIVIDO. Design paradigms for variable distance living</i>	236
Andrea Manca	
Francesca Musanti	
Claudia Pintor	
<i>Maieutic aberrations. Can the heterotopias conceived for historical plagues teach us anything about today's pandemic space?</i>	244
Francesca Musanti	
Claudia Pintor	
Andrea Manca	
Drum Books	255
Dynamic Research on Urban Morphology books DRUM BOOKS	256

Extramural Chapels in the medieval towns of Mecklenburg

Fred Ruchhöft

Regional Museum in Goldberg

Gudrun Ruchhöft

Freelance archaeologist

Martin Ebert

Norwegian University of Life Sciences

martin.ebert@nmbu.no

Philip Hansen

Norwegian University of Life Sciences

philip.h.hansen@nmbu.no

Introduction

Extramural chapels, or charitable foundations with associated hospices and cemeteries, were established as pilgrimage, procession, or expiatory chapels. They are part of the typical image of mediaeval towns in Central Europe. Accordingly, most towns in Mecklenburg had spiritual foundations. While Holy Spirit Hospices were almost always situated inside the mediaeval fortifications because of their early establishment, the tendentially younger foundations (usually St. George and St. Gertrude) were to find *extra muros ante portam*, a few 100 m outside the walls, sometimes even in neighbouring villages, but always on important trade roads.

Status of knowledge

Modern historical research has only marginally touched these foundations, although they were an important, perhaps even a fundamental, part of medieval towns (Struck 1938, 130–137); too often, these objects located outside the town gates got out of sight of urban research. As a result, little is known about them, a fate they share with other suburban establishments such as execution sites, mills, and militias. The extramural hospices in Mecklenburg, or sometimes just their chapels, are often only mentioned incidentally, mostly in connection with real estate transactions and the purchase of annuities. The documents remained relevant as evidence for financial claims well into the 17th century and were therefore recorded again and again and thus preserved. Documents proving their foundation, on the other hand, are rare and hardly meaningful. After the Reformation, many documents were stored in the town halls or, occasionally, in the parishes, which often became the legal successors of the foundations. That is the main reason; they were mostly destroyed in the countless fires of the 17th and 18th centuries. The hospices, with their chapels and cemeteries, were ecclesiastical institutions, but their material provision was provided by the towns or private individuals. They were therefore under the patronage of the town council, which looked after them both legally and economically. Urban hospices quickly developed into municipal institutions (Struck 1938, 132). As far as can be seen, the council took management seriously. According to the structures in other regions, the practical management was the responsibility of a deputy, usually a councilman, while the work in the house was carried out by a hospice manager who lived on site (Struck 1938, 134). The hospice buildings, especially chapels, disappeared, with a few exceptions, during the Reformation. Financed by real estate and annuity property accumulated in the Middle Ages, the hospices continued to exist as poor- or almshouses for a long time. In some cases, property and capital were retained as special assets by the urban parishes. The subsequent buildings, sometimes only lot names, allow the localization of the perished hospices, but unfortunately not in every case and not always precisely enough. However, caution is advised; land lot names can also denote property and do not necessarily reveal the location of the hospice. Therefore, only very few extramural hospice sites in Mecklenburg are listed as archaeological monuments. Accordingly, there is a lack of systematic excavations or documentation accompanying the construction. Only a few chance finds, mostly references to cemeteries, are documented and can often be used as the only evidence for the correct localization. In contrast, the Holy Spirit hospices are located within the old towns, all of which are protected as heritage areas. Archaeological excavations are therefore generally carried out during construction work. Some cemeteries are still preserved as green spaces (St. Gertrude, Rostock),

but people quickly lost awareness of them as burial sites. Many areas were completely built over for precisely these reasons (St. George, Rostock), mostly of them in the 19th or early 20th century. Even cemeteries placed outside the towns at the end of the 18th century were abolished a few decades later for lack of space and suffered the same fate. Barely five decades later, they became building land; the collective memory lasted just two generations (i.e., Goldberg and Teterow, according to various files in the archive of the Mecklenburg church district in the Nordkirche dioecy). This also affected some Jewish cemeteries.

Despite the meager source situation, it was possible to prove for most cities, next to the Holy Spirit hospices not discussed here, the hospices of St. George (Low German "St. Jürgen") and, more rarely, chapels of St. Gertrude and occasionally facilities dedicated to other patrons. If St. George was already reserved for a town parish, St. Nicholas or St. James could represent it with dignity. The first sources originate from the 13th century, at best a few decades after the formation of the town; the majority of evidence relates to documents from the 14th and 15th centuries. Quite a few chapels are only mentioned in the church visitation logs from the Reformation era since 1534 (unpublished sources at Landesarchiv Schwerin). These protocols often contain the only excerpts of lost medieval documents. Information from the era prior to 1500 is missing from some suburban chapels (Goldberg, Grabow, St. Gertrude in Laage, St. Gertrude and St. Catherine in Neubrandenburg, Röbel, Stavenhagen, and many others). Only a minority of towns have any records at all (Brüel, Krakow, Malchow, Marlow, Penzlin, Waren, and others). Some sources are limited to descriptions of neighboring properties (Neukalen: Lisch 1878. We know practically nothing about the organization of hospitals; the documents almost exclusively provide information about the material assets. Occasionally, evidence of vicarages financed by annuity properties in the chapels can be found. It can therefore be assumed that at least one clergyman was permanently based at the hospices. In addition, one can infer from rare notes in early modern church records that the cemeteries were not only reserved for hospice inmates but also served as cemeteries for the poor, especially for residents without civil rights who did not automatically have a burial right in the intramural burial grounds. Since the 18th century, when the population in the towns grew significantly, the importance of the cemeteries of the former extramural hospices increased in this respect (various files in the archive of the Mecklenburg Church District in the Nordkirche dioecy). The only of these cemeteries in northeastern Germany still in use is in Wolgast, Western Pomerania, where the Gothic chapel of St. Gertrude has been preserved. The transformation of extramural hospices probably started when the number of lepers declined during the late Middle Ages. In the course of the 14th century, the term "poorhouse" for the former leper houses increased significantly; in the 15th century, the term "leprosy" disappeared in this context. Only briefly noted that the monasteries also maintained their own hospitals. St. George in Dobbertin (Alsleben 1998) and the Mary-Hospice in Eldena (MUB 9973) are documented.

Epidemics in Mecklenburg in the late Middle Ages

While the state of research on the hospices is sobering, no current studies on the history of epidemics in medieval Mecklenburg, especially the plague, are undertaken. Rather, old reports are referred to, sometimes without further references, or known epidemics are assumed to be given also in the Mecklenburg territories (Spengler 1851; Tott 1855. Schröder 1743 was followed for Wismar and finally for the whole country, who again did not name any sources). It was not possible within the framework of this study to trace the sources in every case. No reliable indications from contemporary legal documents can be ascertained. Even the cause of death of regents follows only chronic reports, which do not always have to be contemporary. Apart from scattered notes, there is only the *Mecklenburg Rhyme Chronicle*, finished around 1379 but only reaching around 1330, and the *Lübeck Chronicles*. (Kirchberg; Lüb. Chron.) All other manuscripts and printed works reporting on epidemic events date from the early modern period, although their sources are not always known. It is therefore often not certain whether outbreaks of the plague are documented for one town, if they can be applied to others, whether they are authentic at all, or whether they really relate to the year indicated. Only the reports from Lübeck and Wismar are comparatively reliable; they can only be accepted for the other *Wendish* Hanseatic towns (Rostock, Stralsund, and Greifswald) with some reservations. The Black Death, which reached the Baltic Sea region in 1350 and is said to have cost the lives of around 50% of the population, at least in Lübeck, is undoubtedly the most reliably documented. The Lübeck

chronicles extensively reported (Lüb. Chron. §681 – Spengler 1851, 14–24). There is only one note for Wismar; no direct reports from the other Hanseatic towns exist (Lüb. Chron. §681, note; Spengler 1851, 14–24). Another instance of the plague reached Lübeck and the seaside towns in 1359; a third wave was documented for Lübeck in 1367 (Lüb. Chron. §698, §729; Spengler 1851, 14–24). The situation beyond the towns on the Baltic coast is difficult to assess. No direct reports or indirect evidence suggest that the Black Death of 1350 spared these regions. In any case, research has shown that members of the knighthood, which is quite well recorded in the documents, did not suffer any losses. At least in the period after 1350, there are not many names missing that were mentioned before 1350. (Pietsch 2019, 411–412) Due to their mobility, the knighthood belonged to a group of people particularly at risk, although living on their estates was somewhat separate from the rest of the rural population. The dendrochronologically comprehensible construction activities in the seaside towns also show no significant demise around 1350; the crisis triggered by climate events in the 2nd decade of the 14th century, which had an after-effect for several decades (Westphal 2002), is clearly more visible. A construction boom in Rostock and Stralsund, which began shortly after 1350 and lasted until the 1370s, is clearly documented (Westphal 2002, Fig. 18 and 21) and is hardly conceivable if half of the population had died shortly before. Unfortunately, corresponding data series from Lübeck and Wismar are missing.

Even less can be determined for the following period (Spengler 1851, 14–24). A plague is mentioned in Wismar in 1376 and then a “cough” (flu?) in 1387, as well as 1391 or 1392 in the *Wendish* cities (Lübeck, Wismar, Rostock, Stralsund, Greifswald). In 1387/88, a plague is said to have broken out not only in Lübeck and Wismar but also in Hamburg and Ribnitz (Koppmann 1887, 95). Lübeck was affected in 1370, 1381, 1388 (Lüb. Chron. §896), 1393, 1397, 1405 (also in Wismar), and 1463 (Spengler 1851, 34). The effects of these epidemics were nowhere near as serious as the first two waves. A total of 21 plague migrations, i.e., one per decade, have been documented for Lübeck and Schleswig-Holstein up to 1548 (Ibs 1994). We can only assume a similar situation for Mecklenburg, but the drastic effects, like the pandemics of 1348–1350 in large parts of Europe, are not to be expected. The knowledgeable local chronicler Wilhelm Mastaler names outbreaks of plague in Güstrow for the years 1350, 1359, 1367, 1463/64, 1529, 1549, 1564/65, 1578, 1580–1582, 1584/85, 1598/99, and later, whereby he only cites documents from the town archives dating to 1598/99. The only general messages are quoted here, but their direct relation to the town of Güstrow has to be in doubt (www.wilhelm-mastaler.de/MM-H2e-GH.htm).

The pogroms against the Jews can provide indirect references to outbreaks of the plague. Jews had lived in Mecklenburg since the 13th century, when they were first expelled from Wismar in 1290 as underlings of Lord Heinrich of Mecklenburg, who, however, ensured their return in 1300 (Latomus ad a. 1301; MUB 2603). A pogrom followed in Krakow around 1325 (Kirchberg c. 178) and then a persecution of Jews in Güstrow, expressly dated 1330 (Kirchberg c. 179). A chapel was erected on the site of the synagogue in Güstrow, which was later converted into a Franciscan monastery around 1500. A chapel commemorating the claimed Krakow host desecration is said to have stood at an unknown location north of the town. It can be easily deduced from the dates of the Jewish persecution that these events have nothing to do with the appearance of the plague. The events in Krakow and Güstrow, which have not been documented elsewhere, were connected to alleged host desecrations. The only connection between the persecution of Jews and the plague is their simultaneity with their expulsion from Wismar in 1290. In other places in Mecklenburg, Jews are proven to have lived in the 1360s and 1370s. Their final expulsion from Mecklenburg only took place after the alleged host desecration in Sternberg in 1492 (last: Röpcke 2019). There is no evidence of epidemic instances in this context.

The formation of suburban chapels

The founding of the chapels outside of the towns can be grasped only on the basis of scarce historical documents. Therefore, the first mentions are only coincidental evidence of their existence. The initial spark for the foundation can hardly be inferred. The first chapels were donated in the 13th century, many decades before the plague first appeared. They are referred to as leper houses (*domus leorosorum*, *hospitalum lepororum*; *lepororium*) and consist of a hospice, a chapel, and a cemetery. Leper hospices were, with few exceptions, consecrated exclusively to the patron saint George, or in German, St. Jürgen. Occasionally they were denoted as a house “for the poor, sick, and lepers (*infecti*

seu leprosi)" (MUB 3597: Güstrow). Leprosy was ubiquitous in the Middle Ages and did not spare the ruling class. Leprosy doesn't spread as an epidemic, so the donations were not dedicated to specific historic events. Though the disease itself is not lethal, those affected usually die of secondary infections. The physically disfigured, who were excluded from society, found shelter in the spiritual foundations outside the town walls. However, other people in need also seem to have been admitted to leprosy hospices.

St. George in Rostock is said to have existed around 1260, but it is mentioned first in 1303 (MUB 2803; 2897; Prang 1840; Koppmann 1887, 94). The Wismar leper house existed in 1260 (MUB 906); it was dedicated to Saint James. An older St. Georg Hospital had already been given up at that time; the "old" cemetery still appears in the city book from 1270 to 1309 (MUB 1562; 1995; 2054; 2370; 3277). It was not far from the town fortifications below the parish church of St. George. More mentions of St. George hospices in other towns have existed since the late 13th century. Overall, it can be stated that almost all towns in Mecklenburg had a leprosy hospital; only in the smallest towns do they seem to not have existed. The missing of evidences of leprosy hospices in some towns (Penzlin, Malchin, and Waren) can be suspected to be related to a lack of tradition (?) or to research gaps. The situation seems to be different with the chapels dedicated to the patroness of travelers, St. Gertrude. They were by far not so present in all towns. For Lübeck, it is assumed that a chapel and a cemetery were laid out after the plague in 1350 (Ibs 1994, 160). Based on the sources, however, this cannot be proven. Due to the lack of tradition and the statistically high probability of plague epidemics, it is not possible to assign the donation of chapels to specific historic events.

St. Gertrude in Rostock dates back to the 1390s (MUB 12685; 12709; 12710; 12891; 12964; 13429; Koppmann 1887, 95 f.). Karl Koppmann traces its foundation back to a plague epidemic that was rampant in the seaside towns in 1387/88. Nevertheless, there is no direct evidence for this correlation in Rostock; St. Gertrude in Hamburg was built in 1391, i.e., shortly after this epidemic (Koppmann 1887, 95). The St. Gertrude hospice in Rostocks Kröpeliner Straße within the town walls, documented in 1468, had no relation to the chapel (Koppmann 1887, 96), but could be a "new hospice" that may have been brought into being shortly before 1400 in connection with the founding of the Carthusian monastery Marienehe near Rostock (MUB 12933).

St. Gertrude in Güstrow was founded around 1430 together with a vicarage (RMU 4406; 4502; 4505; 4566). According to dendrochronological evidence, the well preserved chapel was built in 1439/40 (www.wilhelm-mastaler.de/MM-H2e-GH.htm). The foundation of vicarages was presumably part of the founding act in Sternberg (1447, RMU 7283) and Plau (1468, RMU 13685; 13809), which can be deduced from the events in Güstrow. A connection to a plague epidemic cannot be proven in each case. It can nevertheless not be ruled out that the chapels were built at an arbitrary time on existing plague cemeteries, as soon as a potent donor was found. That seems to have been the case at least in Rostock, probably also in Lübeck; here even with temporal proximity.

One of the rare chapel donations related to a different disease is the smallpox house of St. Lazarus outside the Heringstor gate in Rostock. The house is mentioned in 1522 (Koppmann 1887, 95). No further details are known. All in all, hardly any valid evidence for a causal relation between the plague epidemic and donations to St. Gertrude chapels can be derived from the sources. Only their contemporaneity seems to confirm a possible relationship.

The location of the suburban chapels

The leprosy houses were in general erected outside the town walls, usually several hundred meters from a major town gate connecting them to one of the important arterial roads. The Rostock St. George house was placed south of the town in front of the stone gate on the street leading to Güstrow. The town of Wismar erected St. James hospice (St. George was assigned to one of the municipal parish churches) east of the town, not far from the former parish church of Old-Wismar. Like them, it belonged to the Diocese of Schwerin, while the Wismar town parishes lay under the Diocese of Ratzeburg. St. Nikolas hospice in Parchim is located north of the town across a lowland next to the street to Lübeck and Wismar. The hospice left the street name *St. Nikolai* as a trace of its existence. St. George in Plau, combined with St. Spiritus, was laid out northeast of the town on the old road to Güstrow and Rostock. Coincidentally, in the 1880s, the town council decided to erect a poor house on this spot. Only vague location information from 16th-century sources and a few skeletal finds allowed precise localization. The St. George hospice of Gadebusch was placed west of the town on

the road to Lübeck, on a lot belonging to the neighboring village of Jarmstorf. In 1892, the remains of the towns St. Georg hospice were found while building a sugar factory 950 outside the Burgtor gate of Woldegk (Schüßler 2000, 95). The list of other examples could go on.

A special feature were St. George's hospices, which can be found far outside the towns. Even though they don't fit into the picture of suburban hospices, they were nevertheless always built in the course of the great Hanseatic trade routes. On the road from Lübeck to Wismar, near Dassow, stood the St. George infirmary, which was richly endowed by Lübeck merchants. The 15th-century Gothic chapel, located at the border strip between East and West, was demolished in 1972/73 by the East German border troops (Ende 1980). Although the chapel was related to the place name Dassow, its role on the Baltic trade route had no connection to the nearby village with the same name. Dassow belonged to Mecklenburg but had no town privileges. Likewise, the St. George hospice in Dambeck was situated on the road from Hamburg via Gadebusch to Wismar (RMU 6904; 7892; 9163; 11244). Outside Rostock, in the village of Rövershagen, a hospice with no name existed (MUB 15049; 15101; Krause 1912). In Weitendorf, between Wismar and Grevesmühlen on the road to Lübeck, another St. George's hospice existed. The Gothic chapel is still preserved. Like the chapels in Güstrow, Dassow, and Weitendorf, it featured a rectangular church with a polygonal $\frac{5}{8}$ -shaped western choir. Another peculiarity is St. Georg in Klütz, a market place without town privileges but with its own hospice, mentioned in 1350 (MUB 14829). The chapels in the countryside give us a unique window into the architecture of 15th century hospices, since the chapels outside the gates were mostly removed due to the urban growth of the towns in later centuries. These instances may signal that the hospices were not only for use by the towns; they also covered the needs of travelers in the rural regions.

Special chapel foundations

For special occasions, suburban chapel foundations were established, which were initiated as pilgrimage and atonement chapels. A chapel in front of the Steintor in Friedland was donated by the Dukes Johann and Ulrich of Mecklenburg-Stargard in 1408 as thanks for the victory in the Battle of Karrenberg in 1399 (MUB 13540; RMU 995; 1000; 1653). Also, the burghers of Malchin were to build a chapel of expiation at their own expense. It was part of an atonement contract for the squire and robber Baron Maltzan, who was killed by them in 1385. Since the Malchin burghers did not comply, the Maltzans, a powerful and widespread family in Mecklenburg, built their own chapel on their estate Schorssow, which was first mentioned in 1403 (Schlie V, 64 f., further detailed sources there). The rectangular building made of fieldstone is preserved as a ruin. Processional chapels, like the chapels of Corpus Christi (Corpus Christi) or St. Crucis (Holy Cross), are to be found in isolated cases. They can be classified in a similar way. The Corpus Christi chapel in Güstrow was mentioned in 1332; it was founded probably shortly before (MUB 5378; 5459; 5577). Holy Cross chapels existed in Goldberg (Duge 1883, 64–66) and in Weifin near Neubrandenburg (RMU 8574; 8576). All these chapels are lost. Due to poor sources, more chapels of this type can be suspected. It is also conceivable that open altars or crosses were placed at road crossings and in open fields, similar to those that still can be found in Catholic regions.

Overall, three types of social foundations in medieval towns can be distinguished: Holy Spirit hospices on the periphery of the urban structure as the oldest hospices and poorhouses, which are discussed elsewhere; leprosy houses, mostly under the patron saint St. George; and the youngest, the chapels of St. Gertrude, to which a cemetery for victims of the plague was attached. Various other chapels can be found, while their function not always can be determined with certainty. In addition to substitute patron saints instead of St. George (St. Nicholas, St. James), processional and expiatory chapels exist.

Inventory of extramural chapels in medieval Mecklenburg

Ort	Information	Quelle
Boizenburg	St. Jürgen Hospice, 1301 mentioned, 1630 still existing	Keyser, p. 277 MUB 2756
	St. Gertrud	Keyser, p. 277

Ort	Information	Quelle
	St. Habundus	Keyser, p. 277
Bützow	St. Georgs Hospice, mentioned 1286, chapel vanished after 1544	Keyser, p. 279
Dambeck	Chapel Beata Maria mentioned 1269	Keyser, p. 279
	St. Gertrud, removed in 1619	Keyser, p. 279
	St. Georg hospice on the trade route from Wismar to Lübeck	RMU 6904, 7892.
Dassow	St. Jürgen, mentioned 1368, 15th century chapel was destroyed in 1973	MUB 9742
Friedland	St. Georg outside the Burgtor at the end of the Steindamm, 1387 mentioned	Mayer, p. 61 MUB 11929
	St. Gertrud, christened in 1408, outside the Steintor right hand	Mayer, p. 61
Gadebusch	St. Georg Hospice, mentioned 1327, not existing in 1554	Keyser, p. 287
Gnoien	St. Gertrud, christened 4.Aug. 1400 in Jarmstorf; merged with the Holy Spirit Hospice in G. in 1554, still existing 1804	Paaschen Hane, p. 78
	Holy Cross chapel, 15th C., not existing in 1554	Keyser, p. 287
	Chapel "14 Nothelfer", removed 1539	Keyser, p. 288
	Holy Cross chapel, still existing 1540	Keyser, p. 288
	St. Gertrud chapel, still existing in 1541	Keyser, p. 288
	St. Georges Hospice, built before 1350, ruin in 1662	Keyser, p. 288
	St. Nikolaus Hospice, built before 1350, ruin in 1662	Keyser, p. 288
Grabow	Maria Magdalen-Chapel outside the Mühlentor, ruined in 1656 and removed in 1756.	Keyser, p. 290
	St. Nikolai Chapel, removed in the 17th C.	Keyser, p. 290
Grevesmühlen	St. George Hospice, mentioned in 1283	Keyser, p. 292
	St. Nikolaus Hospice, mentioned in 1283, chapel still present in 1513, the belonging almshouse burnt in 1863	Keyser, p. 292
	Holy Cross chapel, mentioned 1518, 1653 not existent	Keyser, p. 292
	St. Kalvarien chapel, 1653 not existent	Keyser, p. 292
Güstrow	St. Gertrud chapel, 14th C., still existing	Keyser, p. 294
	St. Jürgen, placed on the Northside of the Nebel, mentioned 1313, vanished after 1552	Keyser, p. 294

Ort	Information	Quelle
Klütz	St. Georg hospice, mentioned in	MUB 14829
Krakow	Holy Blood Chapel, outside the town, built 1325, destroyed by lightning in 1503	Keyser, p. 298; Stadtchronik, p. 26
Kröpelin	St. Georg Chapel, mentioned 1440, vanished in 1653	Keyser, p. 299
Laage	St. Jürgen Hospice outside Beeser Tor, chapel in ruins in 1663	Keyser, p. 301
	St. Gertrud chapel, mentioned in 1st half of the 16th C.	Keyser, p. 301
Malchin	Hospice outside the walls at Wargentiner Feld	Böckmann, p. 17
	chapel(s) outside the Mühlentor	Böckmann, p. 11
Malchow	St. Gertrud on the northern bank of the lake, later replaced by the new church in 1870s	Deppe, p. 56
Neu Brandenburg	St. Georgs chapel, donated in 1308, still existing	Keyser, p. 308, Boll, p. 21
	St. Catharinæ, outside the Neues Tor, still present in 1558, ruined in 1631	Boll, p. 21
	St. Gertrud chapel and guest-house for pilgrims, outside Stargarder Tor, donated in 1492 by the major, a merchant, still existing in 1558, destroyed under battle in 1631.	Boll, p. 21
Neu Bukow	St. Jürgen hospice, ca. 1400 mentioned	Keyser, p.310
Neu Kalen	St. Georgs chapel and Hospice, mentioned 1400, chapel destroyed 1638, hospice in use until 1850	Keyser, p. 311
	St. Gertrud, mentioned 1448	Keyser, p. 311
	St. Catherine, mentioned 1448	Keyser, p. 311
	St. Mary, mentioned 1448, still existing 1534	Keyser, p. 311
	Holy Cross chapel, mentioned 1447, still existing 1534	Keyser, p. 311
Parchim	St. Gertrud chapel, removed after 1644	Keyser, p. 314 Augustin, p. 40f
	St. Nikolai hospice, extra muros, 1298 mentioned	MUB 2521
Plau	St. George hospice, mentioned 1298	MUB 2485, 2520
Ribnitz	St. Georg, ruined in the 16th C.	Keyser, p. 320
	St. Jodokus, ruined in the 16th C.	Keyser, p. 320

Ort	Information	Quelle
	St. Gertrud, ruined in the 16th C.	Keyser, p. 320
	Holy Trinity chapel, ruined in the 16th. C.	Keyser, p. 320
	St. Mary, removed 1854	Keyser, p. 320
Röbel	St. Jürgen (st. Georg) Hospice with chapel between Altstadt and Neustadt	Deppe, p. 67 and 76; Schlie V,473
Rostock	St. Georg Hospice for leprosy, dedicated in 1260, vanished between 1618 and 1648	Keyser p. 323
	?	
Schwaan	St. Jürgen chapel, mentioned in 1471	Keyser, p. 327
Schwerin	St. Georg Hospice (St. Jürgen), «domus leprosum», outside the Mühlentor,	Jesse, p. 95 MUB 1672, 2045
	St. Nikolas in the Schelfe, donated 1238, still existing 1397, replaced by early 18th C. by the St. Nikolas church	Jesse, p. 60
	Beghinenhäuser	Jesse, p. 213
Stargard	St. Georg hospice, mentioned 1357 and 1364	MUB 8398, 9291
Stavenhagen	St. Jürgen chapel with attached almshouse, received a donation in the late 16th C.	Keyser, p. 333
Sternberg	St. George Hospice with St. Jürgen chapel, founded before 1361, removed after 1659	Keyser, p. 334 MUB 8879
	St. Gertrud with Almshouse, founded before 1319, still existing in 1930	Keyser, p. 334
Sülze	St. Jürgen chapel, mentioned 1336	Keyser, p. 336
	St. Gertrud	Keyser, p. 336
	Holy Cross chapel	Keyser, p. 336
Teterow	St. Mary outside the Malchiner Tor, mentioned 1514	Keyser, p. 339
	St. Gertrud outside the Malchiner Tor, mentioned 1514	Keyser, p. 339
	St. Georg Chapel with Almshouse outside the Rostocker Tor, mentioned 1514, vanished by the end of the 16th C.	Keyser, p. 339
Waren	St. Jürgen outside the Neues Tor	Deppe, p. 43
Weitendorf	St. Georg hospice on the Hanseatic trade route	MUB 15049

Ort	Information	Quelle
Wismar	St. Georgs hospice, outside the Lübecker Tor	MUB 1995
	Holy Cross chapel, built on the site of the church of Alt-Wismar, late 15th C., removed in 1563	Schlie II, p. 171
	St. Jacobus outside the Lübisches Tor, dedicated to leprosy, removed in 1631	Schlie II, p. 171
Wittenburg	St. Jürgen chapel	Keyser, p. 347
	St. Gertrud chapel	Keyser, p. 347
	Holy Cross chapel	Keyser, p. 347
Woldegk	St. Georg Chapel on the Kapellenberg, vanished in the 16th C.	Landbote, 12/2019 p. 33
	Holy Cross chapel, at the Pfarrkämpen (today Raiffeisen Baumarkt)	Landbote, 12/2019 p. 34

References:

- Alsleben, H. (1998). Salbe gab es an der Klosterpforte. SVZ Lübz – Goldberg – Plau, 6. Januar 1998.
- Wilhelm, D. E. F. (1883). Urkundliche Nachrichten über Goldberg und Umgegend. Gadebusch.
- Ende, H. (2000). Die Kapelle des Siechenhauses in Schwanbeck bei Dassow. In: Mecklenburgia Sacra 3 (2000), p. 126–138.
- Hartwig, J. (1994). Die Pest in Schleswig-Holstein von 1350 bis 1547/48. Eine sozialgeschichtliche Studie über eine wiederkehrende Katastrophe. Frankfurt.
- Kirchberg, E.v. (1996). Mecklenburgische Reimchronik des Ernst von Kirchberg, hg. von C. Cordshagen. Köln [a. o.].
- Koppmann, K. (1887). Geschichte der Stadt Rostock. 1. Theil: Von der Gründung der Stadt bis zum Tode Joachim Slüters (1532). Rostock.
- Krause, L. (1912). Die Siechenkapelle an der Ribnitzer Landstraße und der geschichtliche Kern der Sage von der bettelnden Hexe beim Landkrüge. In: Beiträge zur Geschichte der Stadt Rostock 6, p. (1912), p. 127–142.
- Bernhard Latomus (1745). Genealochronicon Megapolitanum. Omnis Ævi. Historiam Regni, Dynastiæ, Ducatus et Principatus Mecklenburgici Continens. In: Ernst Joachim Westphalen, Monumenta Inedita Rerum Germanicarum Praecipue Cimbricarum, Et Megapolensium, Quibus Varia Antiquitatum, Historiarum, Legum, Juriumque Germaniae, Speciatim Holsatiae Et Megapoleos Vicinarumque Regionum Argumenta Illustrantur, Lipsia, p. 1–530.
- Lisch, G. C. F. (1867). Beiträge zur Geschichte der Stadt Röbel, In: Jahrbücher des Vereins für Mecklenburgische Geschichte und Altertumskunde 32 (1867), p. 149–154.
- Lisch, G. C. F. (1878). Ueber das alte Stadtbuch von Neu-Kalen, 1399–1402, 1414–1417, 1447–1448. In: Jahrbücher des Vereins für Mecklenburgische Geschichte und Altertumskunde 43 (1878), p. 3–26.
- Koppmann, K. (Ed.). Die Chroniken der niedersächsischen Städte, Lübeck ; Vol. 1–5. Die Chroniken der deutschen Städte, Vol. 19; 26; 28; 30; 31). 1884–1914.
- Moseng O. G. (2006). Den flyktige pesten. Vilkårene for epidemier i Norge i seinmiddelalder og tidlig nytid. Oslo.
- Mecklenburgisches Urkundenbuch (MUB), Bd. 1–25. Schwerin 1863–1936, 1977.
- Pietsch, T. (2019). Führende Gruppierungen im spätmittelalterlichen Niederadel Mecklenburgs. Kiel.
- Prang, G. (1840). Hospital zu St. Georg von Rostock. In: Jahrbücher des Vereins für Mecklenburgische Geschichte und Altertumskunde 5 (1840), p. 119–120.
- Landesarchiv Schwerin, 11.11 Regesten mecklenburgischer Urkunden (RMU).
- Röpcke A. (2019). Das Pogrom von Sternberg 1492 und die Folgen. In: M. Mahnke/R. Wiese (ed.),

Erinnerung an Mecklenburg. Köln et al., p. 34–37.

Schlie, F. Die Kunst- und Geschichtsdenkmäler des Großherzogthums Mecklenburg-Schwerin, Vol. 1–5. Schwerin 1896–1905.

Schröder, D. (1743). Kurtze Beschreibung Der Stadt und Herrschafft Wismar. Was betrifft Die Weltliche Historie Derselben. Mehrentheils aus allerhand schriftlichen Urkunden, Zur Erläuterung Der Mecklenburg. Weltlichen Historie, den Liebhabern mitgetheilet. Wismar.

Spengler, L. (1851). Beiträge zur Geschichte des Medicin in Mecklenburg. Wiesbaden.

Struck, W.-H. (1938). Die Geschichte der mittelalterlichen Selbstverwaltung in den mecklenburgischen Landstädten. Schwerin 1938 (Mecklenburgische Jahrbücher 101, Beiheft).

Tott, C. A. (1855). Versuch einer Medicinal-Statistik Mecklenburg-Schwerins. In: Archiv für Landeskunde in den Großherzogthümern Mecklenburg. 5 (1855), p. 1–18.

Wessel, F. (1932). Vom St. Jürgen-Hospital in Tessin. In: Ostmecklenburgische Heimat 5 (1932), 21, p. 165–166.

Westphal, T. (2002). Frühe Stadtentwicklung zwischen mittlerer Elbe und unterer Oder zwischen ca. 1150–1300 aufgrund der dendrochronologischen Daten. Bonn (Universitätsforschungen zur prähistorischen Archäologie 86).

Fig. 1 Map of known sites of extramural hospices in medieval Mecklenburg.

Fig. 2 St. Gertrudes chapel in Güstow. The 15th century Gothic gable, rectangular chapel with a polygonal $\frac{5}{8}$ choir towards west. 3D-Scan by Martin Ebert, NMBU in February 2022.

Fig. 3 Güstrow about 1650, print by Matthäus Merian. The St. Gertrude chapel of Güstrow (marked red) is placed 250 meter outside the Schoientor gate, while the chapel dedicated to Maria right outside the Halbkuksche Tor (center left) was replaced by fortifications.

Fig. 4 The architecture of suburban chapels in Mecklenburg. The buildings are built with bricks, they are almost never vaulted and have mostly a polygonal $\frac{5}{8}$ -shaped choir. Illustration by Martin Ebert.

Ebert, Martin

Associate Professor at Norwegian University of Life Sciences (NMBU). Born 1969 in Germany, practising architect, author and publisher. Researchproject on Urban Morphology in Medieval Mecklenburg (RUMMM). Recent publications: 'Nye vandringer gjennom Landet Meklenburg'. Journal of a morphological excursion through the owns of Mecklenburg' (Norwegian), Ås 2021. 'A methodical approach to the comparative study of planted towns in 13th century Meklenburg', *Forma Civitatis*, 01/2021, p. 56-67. 'Zur Verwendung des Westfälischen Quadrates in mecklenburgischen Hallenkirchen'. *Geometrical mapping an classification of hall-churches in medieval Mecklenburg*, Oslo 2021.

Dr.phil. Ruchhöft, Fred

Born 1971 in Lübz, now director of the regional Museum in Goldberg, Mecklenburg. numerous publications on urban history of medieval towns in Mecklenburg. Dissertation 1999 on 'Die Entwicklung der Kulturlandschaft im Raum Plau-Goldberg im Mittelalter'. Recent publications: Ruchhöft, F. (2018). *Arkona-Glaube, Macht und Krieg im Ostseeraum*. Landesamt für Kultur und Denkmalpflege Mecklenburg-Vorpommern. Ruchhöft, F., Adolph, M. L., Ansorge, J., Bartel, B., Besler, C., Černý, A. & Schult, M. (2017). *Zvarin-Schwerin*. Landesamt für Kultur und Denkmalpflege Mecklenburg-Vorpommern. Ruchhöft, F. (2017). Frühmittelalterliche Handelswege zwischen Sachsen und slawischer Ostseeküste: Transkontinentale Verbindungen im frühen Mittelalter. *Zeitschrift für Archäologie des Mittelalters*, (45), 4.